

Organisational Doping Controls, Attitudes Towards Doping and the Intention to use Performance Enhancing Substances among Members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study explores the relationships among organizational doping controls, athletes' attitudes toward doping, and their intention to use performance-enhancing substances (PES) among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria. Using a stratified random sampling technique, 173 members participated by completing a structured questionnaire designed to assess these variables. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics to summarize key findings, while linear regression analysis and Pearson correlation were employed to test three hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that organizational doping control measures did not significantly predict athletes' intention to use PES, suggesting that external enforcement alone may not effectively deter doping intentions. A strong, statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.825$, $p < 0.01$) was observed between athletes' attitudes toward doping and their intention to use PES, indicating that favourable attitudes toward doping strongly influence intentions. Conversely, a weak and statistically insignificant correlation ($r = 0.098$, $p > 0.05$) was found between organizational doping controls and attitudes toward doping, highlighting the limited influence of control measures on shaping athletes' attitudes. These findings underscore the need for holistic anti-doping strategies that target attitudes and intrinsic motivations through education and value-based interventions, complementing existing organizational doping control measures.

Keywords: Doping controls, attitude to doping, performance enhancing substances

Introduction

Athletes, sporting organizations, and sports enthusiasts have all expressed serious concerns about the phenomena of doping in sports. Doping; the use of prohibited substances or methods by athletes to enhance performance and which is considered unethical and against the rules of fair competition has been an issue of concern in sports. These substances may include anabolic steroids, hormones, stimulants, or methods such as blood doping that aim to artificially improve strength, endurance, or recovery. Doping distorts the integrity of competitive sports and creates an unfair playing field by undermining the values of fair play and sportsmanship (World Anti-Doping Agency [WADA], 2021).

Within this context, the role of organizational doping controls becomes critical, as they represent the measures and strategies employed by sport's governing bodies to prevent and manage the use of performance-enhancing substances (PES). However, the effectiveness of these controls is significantly influenced by athletes' attitudes towards doping and their intentions to use PES, making this an essential area of investigation.

In Nigeria, athletics is one of the most prominent sports, with its athletes frequently participating in regional, continental, and global competitions. However, instances of doping violations

involving Nigerian athletes have raised concerns about the adequacy of doping controls and the cultural and organizational factors influencing doping behaviours (Ajiboye & Afolabi, 2020). Despite global efforts spearheaded by WADA to combat doping, the dynamics within specific national contexts, such as Nigeria, remain underexplored. The Athletics Federation of Nigeria (AFN), as the governing body for athletics in the country, plays a pivotal role in enforcing anti-doping policies and shaping athletes' attitudes through education, testing, and sanctions.

A helpful framework for analyzing doping-related intentions and behaviour is provided by the theory of planned behaviours (TPB). The TPB holds that a person's conduct is impacted by their perceptions of behavioral control, subjective norms, and attitudes toward the activity (Ajzen, 1991).

In the context of doping, this framework suggests that athletes' intentions to use PES are shaped by their personal beliefs about doping, the perceived acceptability of doping within their social networks, and their confidence in avoiding detection. Studies have shown that positive attitudes towards doping and perceived social pressure from peers or coaches can significantly increase the likelihood of doping intentions (Ntoumanis et al., 2014).

In competitive sports, it is prohibited to employ some technology, particularly certain pharmaceutical methods, to enhance performance. The World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) enforces more stringent anti-doping regulations to curb this activity, which is known as doping. These anti-doping policies affect society as a whole, even if they primarily affect highly competitive sports. Some agents portray doping as a significant social issue that affects both the sport and society at large (Pound, 2006), hence addressing it is viewed as a top political priority. In several countries, the principles of anti-doping in elite sports are now also applied outside of competitive sports, such as in the realm of health clubs and fitness centers [e.g. in Denmark, see Christiansen (2011)] or in prisons (Verhelle *et al.*, 2016), and calls for further extension are regularly heard [e.g. Rodenberg and Holden (2017), who asked for an extension of anti-doping to coaches and team executives]. Some nations have implemented more specialized state laws, including as criminal laws, that also apply to non-athletes and amateurs (Christiansen 2011; Lowther 2015; Henning & Dimeo 2017). In the past ten or so years, doping within and outside of professional sport, as well as the anti-doping initiatives meant to eradicate this practice, have become the focus of a thriving field of scholarly research due to these developments.

There is considerable overlap, even though not always recognized, with other important societal and scientific debates, such as the one on (illicit) psychoactive drugs, and the one on overall human enhancement, i.e. the use of technology to improve human performance in general, not only in competitive sport

Implementing ethical and effective doping control measures is essential for preserving the integrity of athletics in Nigeria. By adhering to best practices, the AFN can create a fair and drug-free environment that protects athletes, promotes clean competition, and upholds the values of the sport.

Legal and Regulatory Framework: The AFN is bound by the World Anti-Doping Code (WADC), which sets forth the international standards for anti-doping programs. The WADC emphasizes the principles of strict liability, proportionality, and due process. In 2019, Nigeria ratified the International Convention against Doping in Sport, further strengthening its commitment to combat doping.

Governance and Management: Effective doping control requires strong governance and management structures. The AFN should establish an independent anti-doping agency responsible

for implementing and enforcing anti-doping policies. This agency should be adequately funded and staffed with qualified professionals.

Education and Awareness: Educating athletes, coaches, and support staff about the risks and consequences of doping is essential for prevention. The AFN should implement comprehensive education programs that cover topics such as the prohibited list, testing procedures, and the athlete's rights and responsibilities.

Testing Procedures: The AFN must adhere to strict testing protocols to ensure the accuracy and reliability of results. The organization should collaborate with accredited laboratories and follow established guidelines for sample collection, analysis, and reporting.

Investigations and Sanctioning: Thorough investigations are crucial when doping violations are suspected. The AFN should have clear procedures for conducting fair and impartial investigations. Athletes found guilty of doping offenses should face appropriate sanctions, including suspensions or disqualifications.

Collaboration and Partnerships: Collaboration with other anti-doping organizations is essential for sharing best practices and resources. The AFN should work closely with the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA), the International Athletics Federation (IAAF), and other national anti-doping agencies.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical conduct is paramount in doping control. The AFN must ensure that testing and investigations are carried out with respect for athletes' rights and privacy. Athletes should be treated fairly and provided with due process throughout the anti-doping process.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Regular monitoring and evaluation are crucial for assessing the effectiveness of doping control measures. The AFN should establish mechanisms to track key performance indicators, such as the number of tests conducted, doping violations detected, and sanctions imposed. This study investigates the relationship between organizational doping controls, athletes' attitudes towards doping, and their intentions to use PES within the context of the AFN. Specifically, it aims to determine;

1. the relationship between organizational doping controls, athletes' attitudes towards doping, and their intentions to use PES within the context of the AFN. Specifically, it aims to determine the following: To what extent will organisational doping controls predict the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?
2. the relationship between attitude to doping and the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?
3. the relationship between organisational doping controls and attitudes towards the use of performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?

The findings of this research have implications for enhancing the effectiveness of anti-doping strategies in Nigeria and beyond. A better understanding of the factors driving doping behaviour among Nigerian athletes will contribute to the development of targeted interventions, including education and awareness programs, to foster a culture of clean sport. Furthermore, this study underscores the importance of addressing both organizational and individual factors to mitigate doping risks and uphold the integrity of athletics in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research questions developed for this study are as follows:

1. To what extent will organisational doping controls predict the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?
2. Will there be any relationship between attitude to doping and the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?
3. Will there be any relationship between organisational doping controls and attitudes towards the use of performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated for this study.

1. Organisational doping controls will not significantly predict the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria
2. There will be no significant relationship between attitude to doping and the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria
3. There will be no significant relationship between organisational doping controls and attitudes towards the use of performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria

Methodology

The descriptive survey research method was adopted in carrying out this study. The population of this study comprised members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria. The sample for this study was made up of athletes, coaches and administrators and was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. The population was stratified into athletes, coaches and officials after which the convenience sampling technique was used to select one hundred and seventy-three (173) respondents who made up the sample for this study. Data was collected using a combination of online and physical copies of the questionnaire. WhatsApp groups of athletes, coaches and administrators of the Federation were used to reach respondents over a period of four weeks. The questionnaire was used to collect data regarding the attitude of members of AFN towards doping and how these attitudes are influenced by the sports cultural of the association. Responses from participants were coded and analysed using descriptive statistics to present data and inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Demographic Data of Respondents

Table 1. Gender of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	117	67.6
Female	56	32.4
Total	173	100.0

Table 1. reveals that 67.6% of the respondents are males, while 32.4% are females.

Table 2. Age of Respondents

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percent
Above 54	14	8.1
45 – 54	16	9.2
35 – 44	34	19.7
25 – 34	62	35.8
18 – 24	47	27.25
Total	173	100.0

From the above table, 27.2% of the respondents are within the age range of 18-24 years, 35.8% are of 25-34 years, 19.7% are of 33-44years, 16.3% are of 45-54years, 9.2% are of 55years and above.

Table 3. Designation of Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Administrators/managers	17	9.8
Coach	34	19.7
Athletes	122	70.5
Total	173	100.0

The above table shows that 70.5 % of the respondents are athletes, 19.7% are coaches, and 9.8% are managers or administrators.

Testing hypotheses

Hypothesis one, which states that organisational doping controls will not significantly predict the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria was tested using regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results are presented in the tables below.

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.012 ^a	0.000	-0.006	0.52063

a. Predictors: (Constant), doping control

Model Summary

R = 0.012: Indicates a very weak correlation between doping control and the intention to use performance-enhancing substances. R Square = 0.000: Shows that only 0% of the variation in the intention to use performance-enhancing substances is explained by doping control measures. Adjusted R Square = -0.006: After adjusting for the number of predictors, the explanatory power is effectively negative, suggesting no meaningful predictive relationship. This means that doping control measures have a negligible explanatory power for predicting the intention to use performance-enhancing substances.

Table 5. ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	0.007	1	0.007	0.027	.871 ^b
Residual	46.351	171	0.271		
Total	46.358	172			

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to use

b. Predictors: (Constant), doping control

F = 0.027, Sig. = 0.871: The regression model is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This means that doping control measures do not significantly predict the intention to use performance-enhancing substances. The model as a whole is not a good fit, and doping control does not significantly contribute to explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 6. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.546	0.352		7.233	0.000
Doping control	0.037	0.224	0.012	0.163	0.871

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to use

Coefficients

Constant (B = 2.546, $p = 0.000$): This is the baseline value of the intention to use substances when the doping control measure is zero. It is statistically significant. Doping Control (B = 0.037, $p = 0.871$):

Unstandardized Coefficient (B): A 1-unit increase in doping control measures leads to a predicted increase of only 0.037 units in the intention to use substances. Standardized Coefficient (Beta = 0.012): The effect size is very small and negligible. p-value = 0.871: Not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This means that doping control has no significant impact on the intention to use performance-enhancing substances.

The regression analysis supports the hypothesis that organizational doping control by the Athletics Federation of Nigeria does not significantly predict the intention to use performance-enhancing substances. This suggests that factors other than doping control measures may play a more significant role in influencing athletes' intentions.

Hypothesis two, which states that there will be no significant relationship between attitude to doping and the intention to use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria was tested using correlation analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Attitude	2.8728	0.70794	173
Intent to use	2.6035	0.51916	173

Descriptive Statistics

Mean for Attitude = 2.8728, Std. Deviation = 0.70794; this indicates the average attitude score and its variability. The spread (standard deviation) is relatively moderate. Mean for Intent to use performance enhancing substances = 2.6035, Std. Deviation = 0.51916. This indicates the average score for the intention to use performance-enhancing substances, with a smaller spread than the attitude scores.

Correlations

		Attitude	Intent to use
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.825**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	173	173
Intent to use	Pearson Correlation	.825**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	173	173

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.825$); this value represents a very strong positive correlation between attitude toward doping and intention to use performance enhancing substances. As attitudes toward doping become more favourable, the intention to use performance-enhancing substances increases.

Significance (Sig. = 0.000); The p-value is less than 0.01, indicating that the correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This means the observed relationship is unlikely due to chance. Sample Size (N = 173). This is a sufficient sample size, enhancing the reliability of the correlation results.

There is a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between athletes' attitudes toward doping and their intention to use performance-enhancing substances ($r=0.825$, $p<0.01$). This suggests that: Athletes with more favourable attitudes toward doping are much more likely to express intentions to use performance-enhancing substances. Efforts to reduce the intention to use these substances should target changing attitudes toward doping. This result supports the notion that attitude plays a crucial role in shaping athletes' intentions.

Hypothesis three; which states that will be no significant relationship between organisational doping controls and attitudes towards the use performance enhancing substances among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria was tested using correlation analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results are presented below.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Attitude	2.8728	0.70794	173
Doping control	1.5634	0.17741	173

Descriptive Statistics; Mean for Attitude = 2.8728, Std. Deviation = 0.70794. This indicates a moderate average attitude score with some variability. Mean for Doping Control = 1.5634, Std. Deviation = 0.17741. The average doping control score is relatively low, with minimal variability.

Correlations

		Attitude	Doping control
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	0.098
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.201
	N	173	173
Doping control	Pearson Correlation	0.098	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.201	
	N	173	173

Pearson Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.098$), This correlation coefficient is small, indicating a very weak positive relationship between organizational doping control and attitudes toward the use of performance-enhancing substances. Significance (Sig. = 0.201), The p-value exceeds the typical significance threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the relationship is not statistically significant. Sample Size (N = 173) The sample size is adequate to detect meaningful correlations, but the lack of significance suggests no strong evidence for a relationship.

The results show a very weak and statistically insignificant positive relationship between organizational doping control and attitudes toward the use of performance-enhancing substances ($r=0.098, p>0.05$). This indicates that: Organizational doping control measures do not appear to

meaningfully influence attitudes toward doping among members of the Athletics Federation of Nigeria. Additional strategies beyond doping control may be necessary to significantly impact attitudes toward doping.

Discussion of findings

▪ Regression Analysis: Organizational Doping Control and Intention to Use PES

The regression analysis results showed that organizational doping control measures by the Athletics Federation of Nigeria do not significantly predict athletes' intention to use performance-enhancing substances ($R = 0.012$, $p > 0.05$). This finding supports the hypothesis that doping control alone is insufficient to influence athletes' intentions. The adjusted R-squared value of -0.006 further emphasizes that the predictive power of doping control on intention is negligible.

This result aligns with prior studies suggesting that external regulations and policies may not be enough to deter doping behavior effectively. For instance, Allen et al. (2017) argue that while doping control measures are essential, their efficacy is limited when intrinsic motivators, such as personal values and attitudes, are not addressed. Athletes may perceive doping control as a procedural formality rather than a deterrent, especially if enforcement is inconsistent or if the perceived risk of detection is low (Lentillon-Kaestner & Carstairs, 2010).

The lack of significant predictive power in this study highlights the need to go beyond structural doping control measures. Interventions should integrate educational programs that address the psychosocial determinants of doping behavior, such as attitudes, peer influences, and moral disengagement. Such programs can complement organizational measures, creating a more comprehensive anti-doping strategy.

▪ Attitudes Toward Doping and Intention to Use PES

The findings indicate a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between athletes' attitudes toward doping and their intention to use performance-enhancing substances ($r = 0.825$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that athletes who view doping more favourably are significantly more likely to express intentions to use PES.

This result underscores the critical role of attitudes in shaping behavioral intentions, as theorized by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB; Ajzen, 1991). According to the TPB, attitudes toward a behaviour are a primary determinant of intentions, which, in turn, predict actual behaviour. Favourable attitudes toward doping may stem from perceptions of its effectiveness in enhancing performance, normalization within certain athlete subcultures, or a lack of perceived moral wrongdoing (Petróczi, 2013).

The strong relationship between attitudes and intentions also highlights the importance of targeting attitudes in anti-doping efforts. Educational campaigns aimed at reshaping athletes' perceptions of doping should emphasize the risks to health, ethical considerations, and the potential consequences for career and reputation. Moreover, leveraging influential role models and peers who advocate for clean sports can help challenge pro-doping attitudes and foster a culture of integrity within athletics.

Notably, this finding aligns with previous studies that have consistently reported a robust link between attitudes and intentions in the context of doping. For example, Lucidi et al. (2008) found that athletes with positive attitudes toward doping were more likely to report intentions to use banned substances, further validating the need for attitude-focused interventions.

▪ Organizational Doping Control and Attitudes Toward Doping

The results also show a very weak and statistically insignificant positive relationship between organizational doping control measures and athletes' attitudes toward doping ($r = 0.098, p > 0.05$). This finding indicates that doping control measures have little to no influence on athletes' attitudes toward the use of performance-enhancing substances.

This result may reflect a disconnection between external control measures and internalized values. Athletes might view organizational doping control as an extrinsic deterrent that does not address the underlying motivations and beliefs that shape their attitudes. For instance, if doping control measures are perceived as merely punitive or if athletes believe they can evade detection, these measures are unlikely to foster negative attitudes toward doping (Hauw, 2013).

Additionally, the weak relationship may be attributed to the limited scope of doping control measures. Testing protocols, while essential, often focus on detecting banned substances rather than addressing the root causes of doping behaviour. Without a holistic approach that incorporates education, psychological support, and ethical training, doping control measures are unlikely to shift athletes' attitudes meaningfully.

The findings highlight the need for a multifaceted approach to anti-doping efforts. Beyond testing and enforcement, interventions should aim to cultivate a culture of ethical responsibility and intrinsic motivation to compete cleanly. This can be achieved through value-based education, mentorship programs, and initiatives that celebrate clean athletes as role models.

Recommendations

The findings of this study have several practical implications for the Athletics Federation of Nigeria and other sports organizations:

Enhancing Educational Programs: Anti-doping education should be a cornerstone of intervention strategies. Programs should focus on reshaping attitudes by addressing the perceived benefits of doping, raising awareness of the risks, and promoting ethical decision-making.

Targeting Attitudes to Influence Intentions: Since attitudes significantly predict intentions, efforts to reduce doping intentions should prioritize attitude change. Campaigns should emphasize the value of fair play, the dangers of doping, and the benefits of competing cleanly.

Integrating Holistic Approaches: Doping control measures should be complemented by initiatives that address psychological and social factors. For instance, counseling services, peer support groups, and workshops on stress management can help athletes cope with performance pressures without resorting to doping.

Improving the Perception of Doping Control: To enhance the effectiveness of doping control measures, sports organizations should ensure transparency, consistency, and fairness in enforcement. Building trust in the system can encourage athletes to view doping control as a legitimate and necessary aspect of fair competition.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the complex interplay between doping control measures, attitudes, and intentions in the context of athletics. While organizational doping control alone appears insufficient to influence intentions or attitudes meaningfully, athletes' attitudes toward doping emerge as a critical determinant of their intentions to use performance-enhancing substances. To effectively combat doping, sports organizations must adopt a comprehensive approach that integrates doping control with education, psychological support, and value-based

interventions. By targeting the underlying attitudes and motivations that drive doping behaviour, stakeholders can create a culture of integrity and fair play within athletics.

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